

効果的なEFLのカリキュラムの開発に対して、シミュレーションの重要性.

グレイ・ガヴァン パロリック、 津田塾大学・総合政策部

The Importance of Simulations in Developing Effective EFL Curricula.

Gavan Patrick Gray, Tsuda University, College of Policy Studies

キーワード: シミュレーション, コミュニケーション, TEFL, 英語, 教育

1. The Expansion of Simulations

The field of Simulation is very much a recent phenomenon although its roots stretch back to the 18th century. It was originally advancements in wargames that led the move from the descendants of chess-like games of abstract calculation to more realistic creations which used complex rules, human arbitration or the random element of chance, to mimic real-world conditions in a manner capable of providing practical training and career-related skill development (Shuurman, 2017). Over the past two centuries these 'wargames' developed in both scale and complexity, providing as they did, ever more realistic and reliable simulations of strategic and tactical conditions and outcomes (Smith, 2010). At present, the world's militaries remain one of the primary developers of simulation systems though their application has spread far beyond pure combat scenarios to include situations such as the delivery of Humanitarian Aid and responses to Natural Disasters. The United States military wargaming repository currently holds over 550 carefully constructed and well-supported simulations and their fundamental importance in supporting both planning and training is well-established (Gorak 2016).

By the 1950s, such simulations had begun to spread into the business field with the RAND Corporation taking their experience in military gaming to the corporate world (Bellman, 1957). Since then there has been a considerable widening of the applications found for these tools, such that simulations delivering practical training can be found in use in the teaching of fields as diverse as Caring for the Aged (Hong, 2015), Agriculture (Blank, 1985), Peace Studies (Crookall, 2013), and Political Policy-making (Crookall, 2013).

This paper looks at the application of such tools to the field of Language Learning, specifically that of J-TEFL, the teaching of English as a Foreign Language within Japan. There have been a variety of studies on the efficacy of simulations as tools for language development and in some cases the conclusions

found were mixed. However, in those cases the assessment was based upon examining simulations primarily as a tool for language acquisition. This is not, however, where their strength lies. Their primary purpose is the recreation of real-world scenarios and potential language development is only one of several secondary benefits that they can, potentially, offer. Therefore, in terms of judging their suitability for developing the English ability of non-native students it is very pertinent to ask whether language development alone must be, or should be, the primary goal of such courses. Certainly, language proficiency, especially in English, remains a highly valuable skill for Japanese students to possess. Is it, however, preeminent among skills students should acquire? If not, and if other skills rank equal or even higher in importance how should this be reflected in the way language skills are taught? Whether this would justify using simulations in which pure language development takes second place to the refinement of other skills and abilities is what this paper seeks to address.

2. Current English Education Model

The teaching of EFL is often very slow to adapt to individual innovations and, despite widespread criticism of its functionality, grammar translation remains the most popular method of instruction across the world (Derewianka, 2011: 245). In individual areas, however, more creative approaches are encouraged and explored though even in these cases their ability to initiate significant change is hampered by their centralization of the Four Skills (reading, writing, listening and speaking) as the primary foci of language development for non-native students (Hinkel, 2006).

It might be the case that such patterns work in other countries but in Japan the broad English ability of the general populace, despite decades of extensive English education, remains comparatively low. In the most recent EFI survey of English ability across the world, Japan ranked 37th out of 80 countries, falling within the 'low' skill bracket. This marks a continuing

decline from 2011 when Japan ranked 11th out of 44 countries and placed in the 'moderate' skill bracket. While the 'high' and 'very high' brackets are predictably dominated by European countries there is no reason that a technically advanced state, with strong American influences, should not rank far higher. In 5th place Singapore sits comfortably in the 'very high' bracket. Malaysia (13th) and the Philippines (15th) both rank 'high', while in the moderate bracket India (27th), Hong Kong (29th) and South Korea (30th) all stand above Japan (EF, 2017). This is not simply a reflection of current conditions but the outcome of a long pattern of underperformance in which the major focus of English study is to either enter university or gain a high score on standardized testing. In both cases students study is focused purely on the short-term goal of passing tests and interest in, and subsequently proficiency in, the language frequently wanes dramatically once this short-term goal is complete.

Recently, however, there has been increasing recognition of the importance and practical value of non-language communication skills (such as Intercultural Communication, Negotiation, etc.), areas in which simulation has been shown to have significant benefit as a teaching methodology. This is due to the fact that simulation ensures "that communication is purposeful, in contrast to the inescapable artificiality of so many traditional exercises and drills" requiring "an integrative use of language in which communicating one's meaning takes proper precedence over the mere elements of language learning" (Jones, 1980: 60). What this means is that simulations teach language in a functional way that bypasses any consideration of how effectively the Four Skill are employed by instead asking the much more direct question of "Did it work?" If communication was achieved successfully, regardless of grammar mistakes, mispronunciation or spelling errors, the simulation achieved its goal.

Certainly, in terms of 'perfecting' technical language use, a focus on the Four Skills may be far superior. Yet, this such technical application is largely limited to the answering of standardized tests such as TOEFL or the Eiken, or for sitting university entrance exams. Courses are taught with this in mind and frequently once these narrow goals have been completed (successfully or otherwise) the motive force for continued study wanes. Hence-after, engagement by students often depends upon the inspirational ability of their teacher to a far greater extent than it does on the material they tackle.

More pertinently, for most Japanese language students, technically perfect English will never be a requirement. Even at the highest levels of business or politics, a rudimentary

ability level will suffice as long as it is accompanied by either competence in practical communication skills or area-specific higher-level vocabulary use. In other words, a student with high rankings in each of the Four Skills will remain practically deficient if their underlying interpersonal communication is poor (due to shyness or a lack of confidence, poor understanding of social dynamics, an inability to empathize or recognize non-verbal cues, etc) where a student with lower basic English ability who has studied dedicated Communication skills may be much more comfortable and fluid in expressing themselves. Equally, an advanced English might lack field-specific vocabulary while an intermediate student with lower general English ability, yet, who has practiced using such specialized vocabulary, may be more capable at working within such a field. Purely technical proficiency cannot, therefore, be the sole marker for success. Despite this, it remains the standard aim of most language courses rather than, as should be the case, a measure of student's practical (i.e. real world) proficiency with the language.

It has been found that simulations are useful for merging with existing language teaching methodologies in order to bolster phases of language acquisition in which traditional, formal instruction has proven less effective (Garcia-Carbonell, 2001). This might include areas such as the above communication skills and field-specific vocabulary but the question remains as to which should take precedence; improving pure language ability (i.e. perfecting the Four Skills) or delivering practical career-oriented 'imperfect' proficiency.

3. The Importance of Motivation and Practicality.

One of the major attempts to overturn the stagnant dominance of Four Skills programs in Japan has been the introduction of content-based courses, what is commonly known as Content Language and Integrated Learning (CLIL). It is a major improvement in that it shifts the focus from development of English alone to the concurrent acquisition of other goals, namely the 'content' of the lesson (Coyle, 2010). However, this is also the failing of the program as this content, and the manner in which it is taught is entirely at the whim of the instructors interests and this can lead to students who hope to pursue business careers taking classes in American Literature (in English), or, students majoring in Electrical Engineering sciences studying courses on Environmental Issues (in English). There are certainly benefits to be found in CLIL methodology but it requires a fundamental reassessment of the 'content' chosen for individual courses and the way in which such content is approached.

Recent studies have shown that courses which offer demonstrable career utility are much better at increasing the motivation of students and can also overcome the development of 'generalized' knowledge which lacks specific career relevance (CNE, 2016). A broad-ranging survey of US students found a clear link between student motivation and their ability to "envison a path from their studies to their future work" (Busteed, 2018). It is evident that well designed curricula should, wherever possible, include discernible links between their content and future application of such content by students in their professional lives.

The importance of motivation can be seen in the positive response to the 'Reacting to the Past' series of historical simulations which are becoming increasingly popular in American history courses (Lang, 2015). Professors using the tools frequently report that student's levels of external study, research and preparation, dramatically increase as they become engaged with stimulating material that provides a clear, practical context for the information being transferred in class. Simulations in general have been shown to boost not only student's motivation but their emotional involvement, self-efficacy and satisfaction (Vlachopoulos, 2017).

In terms of language development it can therefore be expected that effective use of simulations will see students engage more heavily in the use of the Four Skills outside of set class times. In the aforementioned Reacting to the Past series, students would spend so many hours outside of class, engaging in peer discussion, writing papers, preparing speeches and watching audio-visual material related to the subjects, that teachers were being asked to limit the amount of extra-curricular time students dedicated to the course. These activities, quite clearly overlap the Four Skills of language learning and it seems evident that if EFL students could be similarly motivated they would certainly make significant practical use of such skills.

The intrinsic language element is, of course, just one benefit that students would be likely to gain and the question again arises of whether it is the English language skills that should be the dominant element of the course goals or whether, in some cases, they should take secondary precedence to other equally, if not more, valuable skills.

4. Simulations and Skill Development

Past comparisons of simulation and class-based language learning have said that there is no significant difference in language gain between the two methods (Randel, 1992), yet, these studies examined only one element of simulations return on investment, the gain made in technical language skills. In contrast, in addition to opportunities to make practical use of

language, simulations also have broad room to introduce other equally useful skills. In determining which are the most valuable to students, post-graduation surveys of such students themselves have found that the vast majority "rate teamwork, communication, data analysis and problem-solving as the most important competences in their professional experience, regardless of their work environment" (Passow, 2012). The same prioritization of skills has been found in employers, such that "the competences most demanded by businesses are among the professional or generic, i.e., problem-solving, autonomy, communication, team-work, working under pressure, initiative, decision-making, together with the ability to adapt to multicultural environments" (Garcia-Carbonell, 2014). These are all skills that simulations can enhance and refine, with the obvious caveat that the success of simulations depend upon their effective design in regards to factors such as: relevance, ease of use, and the presence of sufficient challenge (Adobor, 2006).

Given the above, when the skills that simulations can offer, which are also deemed highly career important, are considered, they include, but are not limited, to the following:

1. Critical Thinking and Logic
2. Problem-Solving and Lateral Thinking
3. Analytical Thinking and Assessment
4. Project Management
5. Teamwork and Leadership
6. Psychology and Emotional Communication
7. Negotiation
8. Conflict Resolution
9. Intercultural Communication

Many others could certainly be added but the above are enough to see that there is significant room for the development of curricula that focus on the development of effective Communication skills as an upmost priority with acquisition of technical English ability being a secondary priority. This does not, however, mean that English is not a priority. By conducting courses in English the acquisition and use of Practical Communicative English would be a key priority, along with the acquisition of some or all of the above skills.

Needless to say that in the creation and development of such a curriculum the use of simulations as a teaching methodology would be a central element, necessitating, from the outset, careful consideration of their fundamental role within the course structure.

5. Simulation as an element of Communication Curricula

In current Japanese universities language courses frequently remain clearly segregated by the elements of the Four Skills being taught, such that there is often no overlap between Reading and Listening, or Speaking and Writing. Some courses have adopted a more integrated 'whole skills' approach and some have acknowledged the increasing importance of pure communication skills by incorporating them into existing courses structures. For most students, however, the reality is that these communicative skills are likely to be far more valuable to them in the long term than simple English proficiency. Ideally, new curricula should be designed that seek to deliver both with the acknowledgement that the communicative element takes precedence over (though by no means excludes) the English language component.

Below is an example of a more standard Four Skills program in which lessons, while they may have some content-based focus that changes from term to term, are squarely aimed at developing specific skill elements as a primary goal.

(A) Typical Four Skill EFL Program

First Year: Reading + Writing + Speaking & Listening

Second Year: Reading + Writing + Speaking & Listening

Third Year: Reading + Writing + Speaking & Listening

In contrast, the following represents what might be called a program for Practical English Communication (PEC). Rather than technical English skill the course goals are aimed at developing specific skills that vary from term to term but build upon those skills that are acquired earlier in the program. While a secondary focus, English remains the language of instruction and the practical, career-oriented focus of the curriculum aims to boost student motivation and interest in using English as a practical, long-term skill.

(B) Practical English Communication Program

*First Year: Public Speaking + Critical Thinking +
Interpersonal Communication*

*Second Year: Negotiation + Conflict Resolution + Media
Production*

*Third Year: Project Management + Leadership Training +
Organizational Politics*

Instead of the long-term aims of the (A) curriculum which aims to boost English proficiency over the course of many years or slow incremental change, the (B) type PEC curriculum offers students clear, short-term progress in a variety of different areas. The variation of fields and clear career application serve to sustain student motivation so that over the long-term they can experience the same incremental

progress in English as the (A) type, without losing their interest in the subject matter during the process.

Selection of courses would clearly vary based upon the specialized field of study of students and their likely career trajectory, yet, the above skills are highly beneficial for a very broad variety of possible jobs and align neatly with the aforementioned capabilities that employers rate most highly. Initial courses would focus upon development of the basic communication tools necessary for effective participation in later courses, for example, areas such as Public Speaking, Presentation Skills and Interpersonal Communication. These would develop in subsequent terms to more professionally focused areas such as Negotiation and Team Management. As students progress, the focus of courses would become more expansive with courses such as Project Management making use of simulations involving an increasing number of participants or more extended timeframe. An entire final course might be given over to a full-term simulation that could act as a graduation project integrating all previously learned skills in the completion of a task mimicking likely career needs, such as developing an advertising campaign or a humanitarian aid program.

At each stage of the PEC curriculum ample opportunities exist for simulations to enhance the learning experience. All of the previously mentioned fields, whether Public Speaking (Javid, Z.J. 2013), Negotiation (Schnurr, 2014), or Management (Haro, 2012), have been shown to benefit in various ways from the use of such training tools. Their ability to reflect real-world situations relevant both to students' lives and their likely future career paths would help boost interest, motivation and satisfaction with course activities, leading in turn to a heightened use of English for practical purposes that would ensure students gain valuable experience in the English use necessary for situations they would be likely to encounter in their ongoing lives.

6. Conclusion

Developing a new curriculum for EFL in Japan, or other countries, is clearly a task with several significant barriers. One of these would be the institutional entropy, risk aversion and general conservatism which makes it difficult to enact broad change, regardless of the efficacy of the new ideas. In addition, many language teachers have invested considerable time in other methodologies and the sunk cost fallacy suggests they would be hesitant to turn their back on such practices even if clear benefits could be plainly shown.

Of course, this is not an 'either or' situation in which only one tool must be selected. Many elements of other pedagogical

approaches, such as CLIL can work smoothly with the use of simulations and/or a PEC curriculum. There is certainly no question of 'bypassing' any skeptical opinions on the benefits of the latter pair. Those unsure of the benefits to be gained would have to be convinced to adopt the use of simulations as a significant component of course design if any meaningful impact was to be made upon learning patterns in the Japanese EFL. The key element, therefore, is that simulations, their variety of application and the significant benefits they offer still remain an area of minor study within the EFL field and it is this lack of awareness, and the lack of extant research highlighting the potential benefits, which is the most serious barrier to overcome.

In contrast, for practitioners and researchers in the fields of Simulation and Gaming, the application of these tools to the area of EFL studies should be seen as a huge opportunity to study the effectiveness of simulations in a wide variety of subject areas. As previously shown, PEC curricula can incorporate a highly varied selection of individual sub-fields. By conducting more research and study into the application of simulations to EFL education, and by making a greater attempt to raise awareness of the clear and important benefits this can provide students, in terms of both communicative skill gain and the acquisition of practical, career-oriented English ability, it would be possible to significantly enhance the practical impact of English teaching in Japan. To do so will require a greater degree of cooperation and mutual research among members of both fields.

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Author Details

Gavan Patrick Gray, Ph.D, is an Associate Professor at Tsuda University's College of Policy Studies (Sendagaya, Tokyo).
Contact: gray@tsuda.ac.jp